

Validation of the KATANA Computational Tool Using Neutron Measurements at the JSI TRIGA Reactor

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ABSTRACT

KATANA is a water activation facility at the Jožef Stefan Institute TRIGA Mark II reactor in Ljubljana, Slovenia, developed to study water activation processes relevant to future fusion systems such as ITER. In this work, the *KATANA computational tool* was validated using time-resolved neutron measurements during a pulsed pump transient operation scenario. In this scenario, the pump operation involved a step change in flow rate from 0 L/s to 0.5 L/s, followed—after a certain duration—by a return to 0 L/s. The decay of ¹⁷N was measured with a ³He detector, and the results showed excellent agreement with model predictions. This agreement confirms that the water activation and decay behaviour in the loop can be accurately modelled by assuming a uniform flow distribution. The validated tool provides a reliable and computationally efficient framework for studying activation transport phenomena, which can be adapted for future fusion cooling loop systems.

Keywords: Water activation, KATANA, Computational tool, ITER, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is widely used as a coolant in nuclear fission and research reactors and is also to be used in future fusion reactors. The most relevant nuclear reactions involved in water activation are ¹⁶O(n, p)¹⁶N, ¹⁷O(n, p)¹⁷N, and ¹⁸O(n, γ)¹⁹O, with the reaction on ¹⁶O being the most extensively studied due to its high natural abundance (99.7 %) and significant activation cross-section [1]. Among the activation products, ¹⁷N, produced via the ¹⁷O(n, p)¹⁷N reaction, plays a particularly important role in fusion-oriented applications because of its short half-life (4.17 s) and emission of high-energy neutrons in the 0.38 MeV–1.7 MeV range [2]. As this reaction requires incident neutron energies above 9 MeV, its occurrence is enhanced in neutron fields with D-T fusion-relevant spectra [3].

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KATANA [4] is a water activation facility located at the Jožef Stefan Institute TRIGA Mark II (JSI TRIGA) reactor in Ljubljana, Slovenia [5]. Since its commissioning at the end of 2023, it has been used to successfully complete several experimental campaigns that have contributed to a better understanding of water activation processes and their modelling. These are important in the context of research in nuclear fusion, particularly for the future operation of the ITER tokamak [6, 7].

The computational characterisation of the ITER cooling loop relies on two complementary approaches: Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and neutronic simulations [8, 9]. As CFD calculations are computationally demanding, a hybrid modelling strategy is employed. Full CFD analysis is applied only in regions where complex mixing, geometry, or turbulence significantly affect transport, while the remaining sections are represented using a simplified model that assumes a uniform flow distribution.

A simulation model of the KATANA water activation loop, known as the *KATANA computational tool*, was developed under the assumption of a uniform water velocity profile. This paper presents its validation using a controlled pump transient scenario conducted at steady reactor power. In this experiment, the pump was initially at rest (0 L s^{-1}), then activated to a flow rate of 0.5 L s^{-1} , and subsequently shut down after approximately 100 s, allowing the flow to return back to 0 L s^{-1} . The close agreement between the measured and calculated KATANA neutron responses confirms the validity of the uniform flow velocity assumption.

In future fusion reactors such as ITER and DEMO, activation of cooling water will be a significant source of prompt radiation, directly affecting shielding design, radiation protection, and operational procedures. System-level analyses of these effects require repeated evaluation of radionuclide production, transport, and decay throughout complex cooling circuits. Although high-fidelity coupled CFD–neutronics simulations can provide detailed local information, their computational cost renders them impractical for routine design and safety studies. Therefore, simplified activation transport models, most notably those assuming uniform flow distributions, are widely used. However, experimental validation of these assumptions under transient operating conditions remains limited.

This work addresses this gap by experimentally validating a simplified computational model of water activation using time-resolved neutron measurements during a controlled pump transient at the KATANA facility. By demonstrating that the dynamic build-up and decay of short-lived ^{17}N can be accurately reproduced without resolving detailed flow non-uniformities, this study provides experimental support for the use of computationally efficient activation transport models.

2. KATANA WATER ACTIVATION FACILITY

The KATANA water activation facility provides a controlled source of high-energy γ -rays (6–7 MeV) and neutrons in the range 0.4 MeV–1.7 MeV. It was developed to enable experimental investigations of water activation phenomena and is designed for flexibility, allowing applications such as calibration of radiation detectors and dosimeters, shielding studies, validation of simulation tools for fusion cooling systems, and measurements of integral cross sections [4, 10, 11].

The facility consists of a closed water activation loop divided into three main components: the inner section, the outer section, and the control panel, as shown schematically in Figure 1. The inner section is installed in the Radial Piercing Port (RPP) of the JSI TRIGA reactor, where neutron interactions produce short-lived radioisotopes in the water. The activated water then circulates through pipes to the outer section, located inside the concrete shielding adjacent to the RPP. This outer section comprises two circuits connected by a three-way valve: a short loop and a longer delay loop. For the experiments described in this work, only the short loop was used, as the radionuclide of interest (^{17}N) has a short half-life. The activated water is continuously monitored in the measurement volume before being recirculated through the pump into the inner section. The system is operated and controlled remotely from the control panel located behind the concrete shielding [4, 12].

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the KATANA water activation loop.

2.1. JSI TRIGA research reactor

At the “Jožef Stefan” Institute, a TRIGA Mark II type research nuclear reactor has been in operation since 1966. The TRIGA Mark II nuclear reactor is a light-water research reactor cooled by natural convection, with a thermal power of 250 kW. In 1991, the reactor underwent a comprehensive upgrade, during which a pulse rod was also installed in the reactor to enable pulsed operation and thus extend the operating power range. Since then, the reactor has been operating successfully in the Slovenian and international research community [5, 13].

Figure 2. JSI TRIGA research reactor tank configuration.

The configuration of the JSI TRIGA Mark II reactor tank is shown in Figure 2. The reactor core is

indicated in orange. The linear channel, shown in green, becomes operable once the reactor reaches 1 W and is located near the Radial Piercing Port, marked in red, where the KATANA irradiation volume is situated.

3. KATANA COMPUTATIONAL TOOL

The *KATANA computational tool* [14] models the water activation loop using a conventional analytical approach, divided into four sections: the irradiation region (inner irradiation Snail), the observation region (outer Snail No. 1), and two transport regions (pipes and pump). Its schematic is presented in Figure 3. The circuit is discretised into uniform volume elements of 21.56 cm^3 , which are sequentially transported through the simulated loop. For each time step Δt , the specific activity of a given isotope in each volume element is updated according to

$$A'_{t+\Delta t} = A'_t e^{-\lambda \Delta t} + R(1 - e^{-\lambda \Delta t}), \quad (1)$$

where A'_t is the isotope-specific activity at time t , λ is the decay constant, and R is the average reaction rate within the region of interest. The latter is defined as

$$R(t) = C(t) \int \Phi(E) \sigma(E) N dE. \quad (2)$$

Here, $C(t)$ denotes the reactor power coefficient, $\Phi(E)$ the neutron flux, $\sigma(E)$ the microscopic cross section, and N the atomic number density of the parent nuclide, calculated using the JSI TRIGA MCNP model [4]. The transport of each volume element proceeds in discrete steps determined by the volumetric flow rate. The irradiation scenario is constructed by the reactor power coefficient C as follows

$$C(t) = \frac{P_{TRIGA}(t)}{P_{full}}, \quad (3)$$

where $P_{TRIGA}(t)$ is the measured reactor power during the experiment, and $P_{full}=250 \text{ kW}$ is the reactor power at which the ^{17}N reaction rates are calculated [15].

Figure 3. KATANA computational tool schematics.

The computational tool is implemented in the *Python* programming language and can model a wide range of irradiation scenarios and loop geometries. Two main loop configurations are available: the short loop, optimized for radionuclides with short half-lives (^{16}N and ^{17}N), and the decay loop, which

enables measurements of longer-lived activation products (^{19}O). In addition, the tool allows simulation of both flow transients and reactor power transients, providing flexibility for benchmarking experiments and validation studies under real experimental conditions [16].

Uncertainties in the *KATANA computational tool* are evaluated by combining contributions from nuclear data uncertainties, statistical uncertainties from Monte Carlo transport calculations, reactor thermal power calibration [17], and errors from averaging reaction rates across the irradiation volume.

4. WATER ACTIVATION EXPERIMENT AND CALCULATION VALIDATION

The experiments with neutrons from the decay of ^{17}N were conducted on October 3, 2025 with reactor core configuration no. 262, and the reactor operating at full power in steady state. During the experiments, a single ^3He detector with a CAEN data acquisition system was used, positioned inside the outer measurement volume, as shown in Figure 1. The KATANA water activation facility was operated in the primary closed water loop configuration (short loop).

Figure 4. KATANA neutron response to flow step change measured with ^3He detector and calculated with KATANA computational tool. The experiment was performed on October 3, 2025.

The count rate of the ^3He detector is calculated from the measured signal spectra by considering the entire spectrum associated with the $^3\text{He}(n,p)^3\text{H}$ reaction and dividing by the measurement time. The KATANA computational tool was used to calculate the ^{17}N activity within Snail No. 1, with a time step of $\Delta t = 0.043$ s. The experimental configuration was modelled using 584 volume elements.

The measurements from the experiment and its simulation are shown in Figure 4. The upper graph displays the measured count rate from the ^3He detector (blue points with error bars) and the corresponding activity predicted by the KATANA computational tool (red line) with its uncertainty band (pink shaded area). The lower graph shows the measured (blue) and computed (red) flow rate evolution during the pump transient. The KATANA operation scenario involved a step increase in flow rate from 0 L s^{-1} to 0.5 L s^{-1} , followed by a return to 0 L s^{-1} after approximately 100 s. The good agreement between measured and simulated responses confirms the capability of the KATANA computational tool to model accurately the dynamic behaviour of activation and decay during transient flow conditions.

The comparison between the measured KATANA neutron response and the computational model shows excellent agreement within the combined experimental and computational uncertainties. The initial transient peak is reproduced with high fidelity, confirming that the model accurately captures the build-up and decay kinetics of ^{17}N . After the pump stops, the calculated and measured signals both follow the exponential decay of activated ^{17}N atoms precisely. The close correspondence between the measured and modelled decay profiles further confirms that the measured signal originates from ^{17}N decay, as its time evolution is fully consistent with the calculated activity of transported ^{17}N atoms.

These results demonstrate that the flow field in the activation loop can be effectively represented by assuming a uniform flow profile in the computational model, as potential non-uniformities in velocity distribution or mixing have a negligible impact on the predicted activity transport and decay behaviour.

5. FUTURE WORK

Future work will focus on extending both the modelling capabilities and the experimental validation to a broader range of radionuclides, more complex geometries, and fusion-relevant operational scenarios. Dedicated experimental campaigns are planned to validate the computational tool for additional water activation products (^{16}N and ^{19}O). The calculated response of KATANA for ^{16}N and ^{19}O to the same irradiation scenario as presented in Section 4 is shown in Figure 5. Experimental validation of these simulations will require adapted measurement strategies, including improved shielding and collimation to restrict the detector field of view to the selected measurement volume, as well as the use of γ radiation detectors suitable for integral measurements in high-intensity radiation fields.

Figure 5. KATANA response to flow step change calculated with KATANA computational tool for radionuclides ^{16}N and ^{19}O .

The initial stage of development will focus on explicitly modelling radiation fields generated by activated water. An MCNP-based model of the measurement volume will be populated with radiation source derived from time-dependent radionuclide concentrations calculated by the KATANA computational tool. This approach will enable the evaluation of transient neutron and gamma radiation fields near the measurement region, directly linking activation transport calculations with radiation field assessments.

Further developments will focus on extending the modelling approach by incorporating complex geometries with enhanced mixing and residence-time distributions. These extensions will allow the assessment of the limits of reduced-order activation transport models and the identification of scenarios in which higher-fidelity coupling with CFD calculations becomes necessary.

Finally, the validated modelling methodology will be progressively applied to the water activation measurements from the JET tokamak, with the ultimate objective of validating activation transport models for ITER cooling systems.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The validation experiments conducted at the KATANA water activation facility have demonstrated that the simplified computational model accurately reproduces the measured time-dependent neutron response of the system. The excellent agreement between the simulated and measured signals confirms that the model reliably captures both the activation build-up and decay kinetics. These results provide strong experimental evidence that the flow field in the KATANA water activation loop can be effectively represented by assuming a uniform flow distribution.

Potential non-uniformities in velocity or mixing within the loop have a negligible influence on the activation transport and decay behaviour, which significantly simplifies future modelling efforts. The validated model therefore provides a robust and computationally efficient framework for predicting activation and decay phenomena in KATANA water activation loop. This work establishes KATANA as a valuable benchmark facility for the development and verification of activation-transport tools applicable to ITER and next-generation fusion devices.

The *KATANA computational tool* will be further upgraded to include more complex geometries and multi-loop configurations. With these extensions, it can be directly applied to simulate coolant activation and radionuclide transport in the cooling systems of future fusion reactors, supporting the design, safety analysis, and operational planning of facilities such as ITER and DEMO.

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